

INVERTASE ENZYME WITH ITS POTENTIAL ROLE IN PLANTS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8163658>

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Received June: 25/2023.

Accepted July: 16/2023.

Published July: 19/2023.

Abstract

Invertase enzyme perform hydrolysis of sucrose into glucose and fructose. Invertase belongs to glycoside hydrolase family 32 (GH32). Invertase involves the determination of its biochemical properties, including enzyme kinetics, substrate specificity, pH and temperature optima, and cofactor requirements. Various techniques such as enzyme assays, protein purification, molecular cloning, and structural analysis have been utilized to unravel the structure-function relationship of invertase. In plants, invertase is involved in numerous physiological processes. It participates in sink/source relationships, regulating the allocation and distribution of carbohydrates among different plant organs. During seed development and germination, invertase activity is essential for the mobilization of stored sucrose, providing energy and carbon for embryo growth. Invertase also plays a role in floral development, influencing pollen tube growth, and facilitating successful fertilization. Additionally, invertase activity is associated with fruit development and ripening, affecting sugar accumulation, flavor, and texture. The regulation of invertase expression and activity is complex and subject to various endogenous and environmental factors. Hormones, sugars, light, developmental cues, and stress conditions modulate invertase gene expression and enzyme activity. Post-translational modifications, such as phosphorylation, glycosylation, and proteolytic processing, also regulate invertase function.

Key Words: Invertase, Enzyme Assay, Germination, Enzyme Kinetics, Glycosylation

Introduction

Enzymes are composite molecules made of a globular protein and mainly present in cells of living organisms. They act as a catalyst in biological system. Enabling the metabolic responses of a being's body. Similarly, sucrose is an enzyme present in our body, which is also commonly known as invertase (invertin, saccharase and sucrase) catalyzes the

hydrolysis, ("inversion") of sucrose and glycosides with the liberation of glucose and fructose.

The term invertase is derived from the fact that a sucrose solution is dextrorotatory, but fructose is highly levorotatory. The mixture after enzyme hydrolysis rotates polarized light to the left, and thus the rotation has become involved. The enzyme is logically referred to as B-fructosidase, because its hydrolysis sugars containing a B-fructose residue (fructose with the β -configuration). According to the classification recommended by the Enzyme Commission of the international union of Biochemistry invertases (β - D- Fructofuranoside fructo-hydrolase) belong to hydrolase and it is fixed in main class 3 (Gayathri et al., 2015). Due to their specificity for the glycosidic bond, they have been placed in subclass 3.2 and have been assigned sub sub-class 3.2.1.

Therefore, generally invertases are called oligo-saccharides due to group specific B-D-fructosidases and numbered as 3.2.1 (Edward et al., 2011). Invertase, especially yeast invertase, has played an outstanding role in the development of modern enzymology (Coculo et al., 2022). The enzyme was extracted from yeast in 1860 by Berthelot. It was recognized as an "unorganized ferment" (Coculo et al., 2022).

Early work on invertase has been of an immense importance for the development of enzyme kinetics (Vu et al., 2008, Ali et al., 2007). Invertase was one of the enzymes treated in 1909 by Sorensen in his fundamental paper on the determination of hydrogen ion concentration and the dependence of enzyme activity on pH (Workman et al. 1983). Working with the invertase, Houdson, Michacelis gave the first theoretical explanation of enzyme activity pH curves.

Although several authors earlier had, more or less hypothetically assumed the existence of enzyme-substrate compounds (Belcarz et al. 2002). The investigation of Michaelis and Menten on yeast invertase activity and its dependence on substrate concentration was the first in which an enzyme-substrate interaction was treated according to modern ideas on chemical equilibrium (Lahiri et al., 2012, Hashizume et al.,2012). Invertases are classified according to their pH optimum and localization. Many plants possess an active extracellular invertase (Kim et al. 2011).

Thus, the enzymes which are exocellular have been mostly considered as enzymes of cell wall particularly involved in translocation of sucrose (Roitsch et al., 2003). Invertases present in intracellular space are may be classified with respect to their pH optima into

invertases acid (pH 3.0-6.5), neutral invertases (pH 7.0) and alkaline invertases (pH above 7.5). Insoluble and soluble invertases has been found in the developing maize endosperm, in carrot, red-beet and potato (Brandao et al., 2002, Neigeborn et al., 1987). Majority of the soluble invertases were found in vacuolar formation collected with a B-glycerol-phosphatase activity. A vacuolar formation showed a raise in sucrose level, glucose and fructose. Stating the fact that invertase and sucrose both were found in the same section together and incidence of invertase regulatory system may be expected (Young et al., 2007).

Essentially soluble invertase have a role in the sucrose intracellular consumption. Since both invertase and sucrose are formed in the vacuole (Roig et al., 2002). Both soluble and insoluble acid forms invertases from a numeral plant have been extracted, purified and their enzymatic properties have been studied (Kotwal et al. 2009). Acid invertases that are soluble are assumed to be vacuoler enzymes, as has been reported from beet roots, carrot, potato, red-beet, cultured tobacco cells (Lenore et al. 1987, Mercier et al; 2002). *Melilotus alba mesophyll*, *Ricinus Connunis* leaves, and Date fruit (Gjerde et al. 2000). In *R. communis*, the activity of soluble invertase present in leaf sheath are mostly observed to be moderated by product of reaction.

The invertase which are insoluble have distinct properties in many plants as compare to soluble invertase containing tissues in same plants. Both the invertases enzyme (soluble and insoluble) shows mostly similar properties in the plants where studies have shown that normally insoluble invertases shows resistance to salts and buffers solubilization. Another study by Arnold, reported a solubilized invertase by preparing borate buffer and treating cell wall of insoluble invertase with it (Ferreira et al., 2016). An additional property of acidic invertase enzyme is their capability to catalyse transfructo-sylation reaction at high concentration of sucrose (Ferreira et al., 2018). The property of acidic invertase was also observed when another plant *Cichorium in tybus L.* roots were purified (Edward et al. 2022). It is believed that neutral invertases occurs in the cytoplasm of majority of living cells of higher plants but not all. A study found considerable amount of neutral insoluble invertase activity in cultured sycamore cells and citrus fruit sugar storage tissues respectively (Ferreira et al., 2018).

A study reported a neutral invertases even in the same tissue coexist with acid invertases. Whereas, alkaline invertase is found in tissue of *Lupinus luteus*, *Ornithopus sativus* and *angustifolius* nodules. The soybean nodules extractions have been seen to comprise of acid and as well as alkaline invertase activity (Ferreira et al., 2018).

Invertase Characterization

Since 1950 a large number of reports on the occurrence of invertase in plant organs have been appeared. In most cases sucrose degradation has been determined quantitatively, and the nature of the enzymes remains unknown. In a few cases the type of sucrose-splitting enzyme has been determined by identification of products. A better knowledge regarding plant invertase is of desirable but considering the fact that majority of this enzyme's properties can only be examined when it is in purified form. Similarly, in some of the growing tissues the acid invertase activity can be studied very simply but by hormonal action might produce the elevated amount of activity in the tissue (Morris et al., 2012). It is reported that 1-fluorosucrose is used as substrate for invertase however it is not used for sucrose synthetase. Likewise, this enzyme is not metabolized or digested by tissue of plant. Subsequently, for ignoring excessive sucrose hydrolysis a monitoring system is essential and this system can only be observed in sugarcane plant. An acid invertase found in sugar-cane plant cell cultures was found an extracellular in nature (Ferreira et al., 2018). Nevertheless, for the sake of advancement of the study, the neutral invertase enzyme's general localization has never been under consideration. Likewise, the optimum value for Ph almost matches to neutral invertase localization enzyme found in cytoplasm (Lyne et al. 1971).

Some studies have reported invertase from several higher plants, which catalyzes both hydrolysis of sucrose and fructosyl transfer. Furthermore, higher plants invertases are enzymes from complex multicellular organisms. The invertase from *Schizophyllum COMnune* (a wood destroying fungus) has the properties like various higher plant invertases (Avila et al., 2022). The conclusion of various authors is that plant invertases are B-fructofuranosidase such as enzymes barley, sugar beet, banana, lucerne roots (Lyne et al. 1971). Studies have found that two trisaccharide and one tetra-saccharide formed by invertase are identical to certain oligosaccharides found in wheat. Enzyme in *Helianthus tuberosus* (Jerusalem artichoke) has been partly purified and enzymatic properties were studied (Avila et al., 2022).

This enzyme was probably not be characterized as an invertase but rather as inulinase. It splits of fructofuraosal residues from inuline and generally from saccharides of the glucosylfructose except sucrose, which is split only very slowly or perhaps not at all. However, sucrose can act as receptor for transfer by the enzyme of fructofuranosyl residues from the susceptible substrates. Studies have characterized soluble acid invertase from crude extract of *Achras sapota* (Chicu) fruit, revealing optimum activity at pH 3.0 and temperature

30°C. the enzyme showed slightly stimulatory effect with calcium and cobalt chloride while Zn*, Mn. Ag', EDTA and 0-phenanthroline were found inhibitory for soluble acid invertase. Later on, Invertase from the *Achras sapota* fruit was extracted and purified, which showed two fractions (invertase I and II). Invertase I and II were observed to be homogeneous by polyacrylamide disc gel electrophoresis (Ferreira et al., 2018).

Invertase Isozymes

Baker's yeast Isozymes

Invertase enzyme found in more than single type in yeasts generally, either intracellular or extracellular Invertase (Lahiri et al., 2012). External invertase which is present in yeast glycoprotein contain around 50% of carbohydrates, 5% of sugar mannose, 3% complex carbohydrate glucosamine however, the internal invertase holds no carbohydrates (Workman., 1983).

The molecular weight of previous one has been observed with 135 KDa whereas the final distinction has a molecular weight with 270 KDa (Ali et al; 2007).

A study reported that in all the cells that are depressed majorly the invertase is external. Nevertheless, the invertase enzyme is intracellular in the completely in repressed state (Ji et al. 2005). The invertase enzyme are distinct in their composition as the arrangement in the sequences of amino acid is different from each other. Specifically, if we look at internal invertase it does not possess the cysteine amino acid. Likewise, these both types of invertases enzymes are inhibited by the iodine media and re-activated via mercaptoethanol. These both types are reported to be inhibited or repressed in a bi-phasic reaction by cyanogen-bromide (Lahiri et al., 2012).

Isoforms of Plants Invertase

Numerous iso-forms bearing Invertase occur through a diverse property such as biochemical and sub-cellular sites in plants (Lahiri et al., 2012). The optimum Ph of invertase enzyme and some other parameters including their solubility and the subcellular localization, isoelectric point are the main basis where it can be stated that plants induced invertase can be classify into 3 sub-groups. There are these 3 biochemical sub-classes in plants of Invertase: the cell-wall bound Invertase, cytoplasmic (i.e., the soluble alkaline), and vacuolar (soluble-acid). The existence of the several isoforms of invertase enzyme in landscape have functionally important and advantageous role in plants (Kim et al. 2011).

Cell Wall Bound Invertase/ Insoluble acid

INAC-INV (Insoluble-acid-Invertase enzyme) is a cell-wall bound invertase enzyme with glycosylated protein that has different molecular weight range (28/64 KDa). This enzyme possesses an optimum temperature of 45°C pH of 4.0. Likewise, it has a 9 isoelectric point. Copper sulphate 6.2 mM act as an inhibitor on insoluble acid invertase (Kim et al. 2011). It is majorly confined in the tissue of pedicel and endosperm basals in maize kernels. It was stated by observing immunological techniques which are elaborated in the regular progress of the maternal-cells and endosperm-cells. In seed development using a material from bean-plant, it was found that seed with thin walls are coat with parenchyma cells. The raffinose/sucrose could act as a substrate because of being member of beta-fructofuranosidases (Belcarz et al. 2002).

Vacuolar Invertase/ Soluble acid

Vacuolar Invertase with acidic pI and pH range 4.5 to 5.0. Sucrose also hydrolyses the stachyose/raffinose which are being a true member of family referred as beta-fructofuranoside. The globular proteins normally lose their activity when they react with ions of heavy metals including silver/mercury (Songpim et al., 2011). A study reported that the non-competitive enzymes inhibitor is the molecule of glucose and similarly it acts as a competitive inhibitor for the molecule of fructose in some cases. The molecular mass of a matured polypeptide (N-glycosylated) is 70 KDa approximately (Hashizume et al.,2012).

Primarily the acid-invertase was cloned from a plant (carrot) and it was found to be cell-wall bound which discovered that the enzyme invertase has different isoforms that are encoded by a several distinct genes. Though it is proved that the proteins which are derived from cDNA sequence of this enzyme expressed some similar feature and the AIV (Soluble acid Invertase) poses more than two isozymes (Hashizume et al.,2012). These isoforms can be purified, extracted, and characterized by a tobacco chitinase or barley lectin, Japanese pear fruit like plants.

In the purification process, some specific activities were observed of cleansed AIV I (Soluble acid Invertase I) and the other one of AIV II (Soluble acid Invertase II) correspondingly (Hashizume et al.,2012). AIV plays a significant organic function associated with the metabolism of sucrose and for mainly hydrolyses of the sucrose for the developmental processes or growth procedures. Nevertheless, the hydrolysis of sucrose by

the help of soluble AIV plays a major role in regulating the osmotic pressure of plants vacuole which is then measured or even controlled by expansion of cell (Ji et al 2005).

Invertase Enzyme of Cytoplasm/Soluble-Alkaline

Soluble-alkaline invertase enzyme is made up of nonglyco-sylated poly peptide that shows low points. The two types of iso-forms are encoded by the help of same gene whereas two products start from a hetero-nuclear m-RNA several splicing. The poly peptides are homo-tetramers in nature (Kulshrestha et al., 2005). By the help of using expression of cDNA, while the amino acid sequence of alkaline soluble Invertase was reduced, the N-terminal peptide signaling lacks and unlike with supplementary invertases types. In contracts other Invertases acids, the alkaline Soluble Invertases are not a family member of beta-fructofuranosidase as they only hydrolyse sucrose. at distinct developmental stages they all are found in almost every plant organ, mainly in the developing tissues and its functions related growth (Fotopoulos et al; 2005).

Role of Invertase in Plants

Osmoregulation and Metabolism of Plant

The running fuel for the respiration of cell, energy and carbon for the generation and synthesis of various compounds, the invertases break sucrose into a simplest sugar/monosaccharide. The invertases of the plant tissues plays a major role in the loading and unloading of sugars such as sucrose found in the phloem for their long-distance pathways by the essential production of sucrose. However. The development of plant cell along with its elongation, growth, nutrition, and osmotic pressure is often stimulated by the hydrolysis of sugar 'sucrose' into a monosaccharide including glucose and fructose. Developments of the plant's roots such as carrot and the elongating stems-beans are the organs of plants. Whereas, high activity of invertase is stated in the growing tissues of elongating plants. The acid-invertase activity is relatively high when correlated with the accumulated hexoses in the fruits sink organs. Therefore, it is reported that a Invertase-acid soluble majorly works as a sugar's composition manager in the post-harvest methods (Sturm et al., 1999).

Allocation of Sucrose

Molecular physiology of photo synthetics was studied, which reported that the portioning and unloading during the development of seed i.e., fava bean and suggested that there is an

elevated range of hexoses sugar in the tissues including apoplastic-endospermal and cotyledons when studied in the prior storage phase. The level of hexoses was observed to be in proportion. The invertase present in the coat of the seed has been reported to be in approximately equal proportion with the level of invertase present in the cell-wall of the plant (Li et al., 2012). Similarly, it is seen that the deficiency of invertase enzyme and its activity leads to the degeneration of endosperm cells and a primary withdraw of maternal-cells which fallouts in a transport disruption in the plant (Kaur et al;2012).

Invertase Helps in Plant Development

The enzyme invertase is reported to perform the major role in the growth and development of plant by controlling metabolic fluxes and sugar composition in the initial stages. Isoenzymes of invertase i.e., vacuolar Invertase and cell-wall invertase plays the significant role in partitioning of sucrose sugar as well as in the development of the plant's leaves (Ji et al., 2005). For instance, the activity of invertase can be observed prominently during the plant growth in order to improve the level of energy and requirements of carbon to bear the biochemical reactions which elaborates on an adjacent ratio and relationship in levels of invertases and rate of growth. The degradation of sugars (carbohydrate) is also observed in the tissue which is comparative to the respiration, and protein and biosynthesis of cell-wall during the growth period (Hashizume et al.,2012).

Invertase Role in Defense-mechanism

A link reaction can be found in between anabolism of carbohydrate as well as in pathogen responses done by invertases which may also indicates the resistance related to elevated levels of sugars. These studies state that the genes which act during the exposure to pathogen or during pathogenesis are highly under influence and can be downregulated or upregulated in these conditions. They are sugar inducible genes and get expressed above than normal expression in some parts including apoplast of plant Kaur et al., 2012). This phenomenon gives a consequence as an elevated function of PR (Pathogen Related) proteins and hence raised level of resistance in contradiction of the viral infections (Belcarz et al. 2002). The phytohormones induces some extracellular Invertase regulation and also contribute to plant responses associated with reaction of several genes related to defense action and pathogenesis (Kim et al. 2011). The invertase induces the extra-cellular sugars which provides a process for mechanism and supports as well as increase the concentration of sugar. This process then encourages PR-genes of plants and suppresses genes of

photosynthesis, in response to the signals subsequent from the reaction of pathogen (Roitsch et al., 2003).

Invertase Mechanism Found in Yeast

The glycosidic oxygen atom is protonated by an imidazolium cation. The departure of natural group of alcohol will leave an unbalanced carbonium ion as an intermediate product which speculates the deficiency of electrons and distributes in the ring oxygen atom together with the C-2 atom left behind. The carboxylate anion active-site will work in between this and the initial or prior stage by alleviating the species that are deficient in electrons [Figure. 1]. In the next step to get a fructose sugar or fructoside the C-2 cation gets attacked by a nucleophilic atom of oxygen from a water or alcohol (Shall et al., 1971).

Fig. 1 – Mechanism of Invertase.

Figure.1. Mechanism of Invertase Enzyme

Invertase Regulation in Plants

By Phytohormones

A central role is played by Gibberellic-acid in regulating levels of Invertase referred as (GA3). It regulates and promotes the cell elongation process which is crucial for the induction of flower. An elevated activity of invertases has been observed in several organs of plant including sugarcane stem, epicotyls lentil, beet roots, internodes of oat/beans, etc (Li et al., 20112). Cytokinin stimulates the cell growth and therefore, for active growth of cell an enhanced demand is needed for carbohydrate. This phenomenon states extracellular-

invertase higher activity in the tissues (rapidly growing tissues). This also comprises of cytokinin-phytohormones higher concentration. Phytohormones also includes Ethylene for the stimulation extracellular invertase (Fotopoulos et al., 2005).

Under Abiotic Stress

The salt stressed conditions induce the photo-assimilates in plants cell which leads to sustain their vital metabolism process such as maintenance, osmotic adjustment etc. In the source leaves the elevation of sucrose appears with a decline rate of photosynthesis because of the feedback-inhibition underneath the saline condition. A vital role is played by extracellular invertase, in some species by breaking down the sucrose (Roitsch et al., 2003). The gradual decrease in the crop productions and the export of assimilates appears under the stress of water because of huge changes in reaction of source-link. In maize pollination and initial development of kernel these elevated activities of both soluble-invertases and insoluble-invertases gets jammed (Roitsch et al., 2003).

Furthermore, in drought seasons the activity of invertases found in the cell-wall of plant in mature leaves of maize does not get affected, though in vacuole an increased invertases activity can be seen which then leads to accretion of hexoses sugars in the leaves of the plants (Kaur et al., 2012).

In the tips of root maize low oxygen stress decreases Invertase expression and consequently, it decreases the rate of Invertase/sucrose. Hence, by conserving ATP and sucrose and the reduction of signaling system of sugar that are hexose-based, plants adapted to low-oxygen level condition.

Substrate Invertases

In enzyme reaction the choice of substrate is very critical generally sucrose is used as a substrate for the identification and determination of activities of invertases (Kim et al. 2011). A research study has determined invertase activity from *Saccharomyces rouxii* using raffinose as substrate which is catalysed into fructose and melibiose. Acid invertases of cultured tobacco cells were found capable to hydrolyse raffinose, melezitose and trehalose in 77%, 89.1% and 8% respectively (Roitsch et al., 2003). Purified invertase of *Achras sapota* fruit were observed 100% active towards sucrose, 88% with raffinose and 80% with stachyose, whereas these were not capable to hydrolyse cellobiose, inulin and maltose. Purified wine invertase was found fully active on sucrose while 28% with raffinose. The

enzyme was found inactive on other disaccharides. The invertase purified from *P. anomala* was showed 100% hydrolytic activity towards sucrose while 28% with raffinose. the enzyme was found inactive with inulin or melezitose (Roitsch et al., 2003). Acid invertase from *Tropaeolum majus* leaves did not display hydrolytic activities with melibiose, α -methyl glucoside, trehalose, turanose, maltose, inulin or Levan (Songpim et al., 2011). By these results it was suggested that enzyme attacks only on the β -fructofuranosidases with terminal residues of fructose. alkaline purified invertases from Soybean nodulees were found inactive with cellobiose, gentiobiose, maltose, turanose, lactose, mellezitose, α -trehalose, α -methyl-D-glucopyranoside, and β -methyl-D-glucopythanoside, whereas enzyme was found less active with raffinose 2 % and stachyose 1.5% (Kaur et al., 2012). A study has identified invertase activity from *Aspergillus oryzae* using raffinose as a substrate which was hydrolysed into melibiose and fructose. Whereas, melezitose was not hydrolysed by the purified enzyme (Hashizume et al.,2012). Therefore, it was confirmed that the purified enzyme was specific for β -fructosyl groups. Soluble and particulate invertases from developing maize. Kernels catalysed either raffinose or sugar sucrose but not α -methyl glucose or the melezitose. It is appeared both enzymes are β -fructofuransidases and not the glucoside-invertases (Kulshrestha et al., 2005).

Significances of Invertase Enzyme

A mixture which is equimolar of glucose (invert syrup) and fructose produced by the process of hydrolysis related to sucrose is way much sweeter than actual sucrose because of its high degree of fructose sugariness and consequently the content of sugar can be raised without material crystallization (Uma et al, 2010). The sugar which gives non-crystallizable syrup, production from 'sucrose' is one of the major significances from Invertase enzyme among all. Hygroscopic properties are carried by Invert syrup making it beneficial in the process of candies manufacturing which are soft- centred as a humectant (Fotopoulos et al., 2005).

The lactic acid, glycerol and alcoholic beverages etc. requires the use of Invertase enzyme which is generated by the process of sucrose fermentation containing substrates (Ji et al., 2005). For the hydrolysis of inulin (poly-fructose) it requires insulinase enzyme to convert it into fructose (Oberwinler et al., 2005). Other uses of the enzyme is observed in pharmaceutical industries and drugs. Similarly, this is used in the production of non-natural honey as well as for plasticizing agents which are then used in cosmetics (Lahiri et al., 2012). Detection of sucrose is done by electrodes of enzyme. The production of coloured impurities and flavouring agents that are not desired, do not take part on sucrose enzymatic hydrolysis

in the place of acid hydrolysis (Linda et al., 2007). for the continues sucrose hydrolysis invertase that are Immobilized is utilized, and the subsequent shifts of the PH could be utilized to prevent or even avoid the oligosaccharides construction, by the transferase activity related to the soluble enzyme (Kotwal et al., 2009). In aids invertase being a prevailing an anti-oxidant for the inhibition of infestations associated with bacteria and fermentation in gut caused due to oxidation, as well as anti-microbial agent plays an important role. Raw honey was utilized in ancient India for reducing intestinal ailments, killing bacteria and even was prescribed to the patients with a weak heart (Kulshrestha et al., 2005).

It could also be operated in subsidence of bacterial disorders and infections since it has the capability to extract the moistness from the body of sufferer. A study reported from the European country on 18000 patients stated that sugar of honey has an effective tendency in treatment of disease and infection related to the respirational tract such as allergies, asthma, and bronchitis. The Invertases with added enzymes has also reported to assist the remedy for flu, colds and many other ailments associated with respiratory (Kulshrestha et al., 2005).

Conclusion

The characterization and regulation of invertase enzyme and its role in plants provide valuable insights into plant physiology and metabolism. Further research is needed to explore the regulatory networks controlling invertase expression and activity and to elucidate the interplay between invertase and other carbohydrate-related enzymes and pathways. This knowledge will contribute to the development of strategies for enhancing crop yield, nutritional quality, and stress resilience in plants.

References

- Ali, S., & Haq, I. (2007). Kinetics of improved extracellular β -d-fructofuranosidase fructohydrolase production by a derepressed *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *Letters in applied microbiology*, 45(2), 160-167.
- Avila, T. L., Toralles, R. P., Jansen, E. T., Ferreira, M. V., Kuhn, C. R., & Ruiz, W. A. (2022). Extraction, purification and characterization of invertase from *Candida guilliermondii* isolated from peach solid wastes. *Revista Brasileira de Fruticultura*, 44.
- Belcarz, A., Ginalska, G., Lobarzewski, J., & Penel, C. (2002). The novel non-glycosylated invertase from *Candida utilis* (the properties and the conditions of production and

purification). *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Protein Structure and Molecular Enzymology*, 1594(1), 40-53.

- Brandao, R. L., Etchebehere, L., Queiroz, C. C., Tropia, M. J., Ernandes, J. R., Gonçalves, T. & Castro, I. M. (2002). Evidence for involvement of *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* protein kinase C in glucose induction of HXT genes and derepression of SUC2. *FEMS yeast research*, 2(2), 93-102.
- Coculo, D., & Lionetti, V. (2022). The Plant Invertase/Pectin Methylesterase Inhibitor Superfamily. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 13, 863892-863892
- Edward F. The Health Benefits Of Invertase. <http://www.globalhealingcenter.com/natural-health/invertase/> [Published on July 1, 2011, Last Updated on August 7, 2013]
- Ferreira, M. V., AVILA, T. L. D., Kuhn, C. R., Toralles, R. P., & Rombaldi, C. V. (2016). Identifying yeast isolated from spoiled peach puree and assessment of its batch culture for invertase production. *Food Science and Technology*, 36, 701-708.
- Ferreira, M. V., Rossler, A. F., Toralles, R. P., Ruiz, W. A., & Rombaldi, C. V. (2018). Extracción optimizada y purificación parcial de invertasa aislada de *S. Cerevisiae* en puré de durazno. *Revista Brasileira de Fruticultura*, 40.
- Fotopoulos, V. A. S. I. L. E. I. O. S. (2005). Plant invertases: structure, function and regulation of a diverse enzyme family. *J Biol Res*, 4, 127-137.
- Gayathri, T., & Nair, A. S. (2015). Purification and characterization of polygalacturonase from ripened fruits of *Musa acuminata* cultivar from Kerala (*Musa acuminata* cv. Palayankodan). *Journal of Food Measurement and Characterization*, 9(2), 233-239.
- Gjerde Douglas T, Fritzx James S. Ion Chromatography. Weinheim: Wiley-VCH; 2000, ISBN 3-527-29914-9; 2000
- Hashizume, H., Tanase, K., Shiratake, K., Mori, H., & Yamaki, S. (2003). Purification and characterization of two soluble acid invertase isozymes from Japanese pear fruit. *Phytochemistry*, 63(2), 125-129.
- Ji, X., Van den Ende, W., Van Laere, A., Cheng, S., & Bennett, J. (2005). Structure, evolution, and expression of the two invertase gene families of rice. *Journal of molecular evolution*, 60(5), 615-634.
- Kaur, H., Gupta, A. K., Kaur, N., & Sandhu, J. S. (2012). High acid invertase activity for a prolonged period in developing seeds/podwall of wild chickpea is detrimental to seed filling.
- Kim, D., Lee, G., Chang, M., Park, J., Chung, Y., Lee, S., & Lee, T. K. (2011). Purification and biochemical characterization of insoluble acid invertase (INAC-INV) from pea seedlings. *Journal of agricultural and food chemistry*, 59(20), 11228-11233.

- Kotwal, S. M., & Shankar, V. (2009). Immobilized invertase. *Biotechnology Advances*, 27(4), 311-322
- Kulshrestha, S., Tyagi, P., Sindhi, V., & Yadavilli, K. S. (2013). Invertase and its applications—a brief review. *Journal of Pharmacy Research*, 7(9), 792-797.
- Lahiri, S., Basu, A., Sengupta, S., Banerjee, S., Dutta, T., Soren, D., & Ghosh, A. K. (2012). Purification and characterization of a trehalase–invertase enzyme with dual activity from *Candida utilis*. *Archives of biochemistry and biophysics*, 522(2), 90-99.
- Lenore Neigeborn, Marian Carlson. Mutations causing constitutive invertase synthesis in yeast: genetic interactions with *snf* mutations. *Genetics*. 1987 Feb;115(2):247e253.
- Li, Z., Palmer, W. M., Martin, A. P., Wang, R., Rainsford, F., Jin, Y., ... & Ruan, Y. L. (2012). High invertase activity in tomato reproductive organs correlates with enhanced sucrose import into, and heat tolerance of, young fruit. *Journal of experimental botany*, 63(3), 1155-1166.
- Linda, Y., & Cauvain Stanley, P. (2007). Technology of Bread Making In: The Scientific Name for Baker's Yeast Is *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae*.
- Lyne, R. L., & ap Rees, T. (1971). Phytochemistry, 10, 2593 CARBOHYDRATE BREAKDOWN. *IN PLANTS*, 125.
- Mercier-Bonin, M., & Fonade, C. (2002). Enzyme recovery during gas/liquid two-phase flow microfiltration of enzyme/yeast mixtures. *Biotechnology and bioengineering*, 80(6), 610-621.
- Morris, D. A. (2017). Hormonal regulation of source-sink relationships: an overview of potential control mechanisms. *Photoassimilate distribution in plants and crops*, 441-466.
- Neigeborn, L., & Carlson, M. (1987). Mutations causing constitutive invertase synthesis in yeast: genetic interactions with *snf* mutations. *Genetics*, 115(2), 247-253.
- Oberwinler, F. (2015, September). How to understand cryptogams? The development of research methods and their impact on the knowledge of cryptogams. In *Biodiversity and Ecology of Fungi, Lichens, and Mosses. Kerner von Marilaun Workshop* (pp. 106-186).
- Roig, P., & Gozalbo, D. (2002). *Candida albicans* UBI3 and UBI4 promoter regions confer differential regulation of invertase production to *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* cells in response to stress. *International Microbiology*, 5(1), 33-36.
- Roitsch, T., Balibrea, M. E., Hofmann, M., Proels, R., & Sinha, A. K. (2003). Extracellular invertase: key metabolic enzyme and PR protein. *Journal of experimental botany*, 54(382), 513-524.

- Shall, S., & WAHEED, A. B. A. (1971). The mechanism of action of yeast invertase. *Biochemical Journal*, 122(1), 19P.
- Songpim, M., Vaithanomsat, P., Vanichsriratana, W., & Sirisansaneeyakul, S. (2011). Enhancement of Inulinase and Invertase Production from a Newly Isolated *Candida guilliermondii* TISTR 584. *Agriculture and Natural Resources*, 45(4), 675-685.
- Sturm, A. (1999). Invertases. Primary structures, functions, and roles in plant development and sucrose partitioning. *Plant physiology*, 121(1), 1-8.
- Uma, C., Gomathi, D., Muthulakshmi, C., & Gopalakrishnan, V. K. (2010). Production, purification and characterization of invertase by *Aspergillus flavus* using fruit peel waste as substrate. *Adv Biol Res*, 4(1), 31-36.
- Vu TKH, Le VVM. Biochemical studies on the immobilization of the enzyme invertase (EC.3.2.1.26) in alginate gel and its kinetics. *ASEAN Food J.* 2008;15(1):73e78.
- Vu TKH, Le VVM. Biochemical studies on the immobilization of the enzyme invertase (EC.3.2.1.26) in alginate gel and its kinetics. *ASEAN Food J.* 2008;15(1):73e78.
- Workman, W. E., & Day, D. F. (1983). Purification and properties of the β -fructofuranosidase from *Kluyveromyces fragilis*. *FEBS letters*, 160(1-2), 16-20.
- Young Linda, Cauvain Stanley P. *Technology of Bread Making*In: The Scientific Name for Baker's Yeast Is *Saccharomyces Cerevisiae*. Berlin: Springer; 2007, ISBN 0-387-38563-0; 200